

Supporting Information

Synthesis and Biological Evaluation of Pyrrolidine Functionalized Nucleoside

Analogs

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Instrumentation.

NMR characterization. NMR spectra were acquired with a Varian Inova 400 MHz spectrometer (Varian Inc) or Bruker Advance 400 MHz instrument (Bruker BioSpin) using DMSO-d₆ (Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, Inc) or D₂O (Cambridge Isotope Laboratories, Inc) as a solvent.

HPLC purification. HPLC purification of compounds synthesized in this study was carried out with an Agilent Technologies model 1100 HPLC system equipped with a photodiode array UV detector. Unless specified otherwise, UV absorbance was monitored at 254 nm.

HPLC System 1. HPLC purification of compounds **1-17** was carried out using a semi-preparative Zorbax Eclipse XDB-C18 column (9.4 mm x 250 mm, 5 μm, Agilent Technologies, Inc., eluted with a linear gradient of acetonitrile (B) in water (A) at a flow rate of 3 mL/min.

HPLC System 2. Compounds **8** and **9** monophosphates (**8-MP** and **9-MP**) were purified by reversed phase semi-preparative HPLC using a Synergi 4u Hydro-RP 80A column (10 mm x 250 mm, Phenomenex Inc) eluted at a flow rate of 3 mL/min and maintained at 25°C using 150 mM ammonium acetate (A) and MeOH (B). Solvent composition was held at 0% B was used for the first two minutes of each run followed by a linear gradient of 0% to 7% B in 10 min and an increase to 67% B over the next 20 min. The column was maintained at 67% B over the next three min., after which the gradient was increased linearly to 77% B over the next 15 min., followed by column equilibration at 0% B for 15 min.

Tandem mass spectrometry characterization. All synthetic compounds were characterized by MS, MS² and MS³ using an Agilent MSD SL ion trap mass spectrometer (Agilent Technologies, Inc). The instrument was operated in the ESI⁺ mode. Target ion abundance value was set to 30,000, the maximum accumulation time was 300 milliseconds, and 6 scans were taken per average. A typical fragmentation amplitude was 0.7 V, with a scan width of 1.2 *m/z*. Nitrogen was used as a nebulizing (15 psi) and a drying gas (5 L/min, 200 °C). Electrospray ionization was achieved at a spray voltage of 3-3.5 kV. Samples were dissolved in a 1:1 mixture of ACN and 0.1% acetic acid and infused at a flow rate of 10-15 μL/min using a syringe pump. The mass spectrometer was operated in a full scan mode over the range of *m/z* 15-600.

Accurate mass measurements. High resolution mass spectra were obtained using a Bruker BioTOF II (Bruker Corp.), a reflectron electrospray ionization-time of flight instrument operated in the ESI⁺ mode. HPLC purified nucleoside analogs were dissolved in MeOH and infused using a syringe pump. Poly(ethyleneglycol) (average molar mass = 200) was used as the internal calibrant. Data processing was done by using Bruker Daltonics software.

Table S1. Accurate mass data for compounds **1-17** obtained by ESI-TOF analysis.

compound	formula M+H	m/z calc	m/z obs	Error/ppm
1a	C14H20N5O5	338.1464	338.14630	-1.18
1b	C14H20N5O5	338.1464	338.14571	0.56
1c	C14H20N5O5	338.1464	338.14556	1.01
2a	C14H20N5O4	322.1515	322.15070	0.87
2b	C14H20N5O4	322.1515	322.15068	0.93
3	C14H19FN5O3	324.1472	324.14860	-4.34
5	C14H21N6O5	353.1573	353.15670	1.82
6	C13H20N3O6	314.1352	314.12780	23.59
7	C14H22N3O6	328.1509	328.14860	6.89
8	C14H22N3O4	296.1610	296.16010	3.15
9	C13H20N3O4	282.1454	282.14550	-0.42
10	C14H20N5O4	322.1515	322.14730	13.13
11	C13H20N3O5	298.1403	298.13960	2.34
12	C14H22N3O5	312.1559	312.15560	0.96
13	C14H22N3O3	280.1661	280.16360	8.92
15	C8H12N3O	166.0980	166.09870	-4.21
16	C9H15N4O	195.1246	195.12365	2.00
17	C12H17F2N4	255.1421	255.14230	-0.78

Table S2. Anti-HSV testing results for pyrrolidine substituted nucleosides prepared in this study.

Compound	% Cell viability	
	50 μM	100 μM
1a	105.7 \pm 29.0	77.3 \pm 10.9
1b	131.4 \pm 17.6	95.8 \pm 15.3
1c	143.8 \pm 16.0	80.5 \pm 8.5
2a	106.2 \pm 21.6	73.6 \pm 4.1
2b	119.2 \pm 16.6	80.4 \pm 10.0
3	124.7 \pm 21.8	93.9 \pm 7.3
5	159.0 \pm 17.0	124.1 \pm 17.7
6	126.9 \pm 2.9	97.9 \pm 8.0
10	152.6 \pm 19.2	120.5 \pm 12.0
Control	100 \pm 14.1	100 \pm 14.1

Table S3. Percentages of viable DU145 cancer cells following treatment with analogs **1-10**.

Compound	% Cell viability			
	50 μ M		100 μ M	
	Trial 1	Trial 2	Trial 1	Trial 2
1a	105.7 \pm 29.0	116.2 \pm 9.7	77.3 \pm 10.9	99.7 \pm 11.0
1b	131.4 \pm 17.6	114.0 \pm 14.7	95.8 \pm 15.3	77.8 \pm 13.3
1c	143.8 \pm 16.0	107.3 \pm 7.3	80.5 \pm 8.5	83.6 \pm 9.2
2a	106.2 \pm 21.6	97.4 \pm 5.0	73.6 \pm 4.1	73.9 \pm 11.1
2b	119.2 \pm 16.6	95.0 \pm 5.3	80.4 \pm 10.0	74.5 \pm 2.1
3	124.7 \pm 21.8	96.2 \pm 21.2	93.9 \pm 7.3	67.8 \pm 3.3
5	159.0 \pm 17.0	108.5 \pm 9.0	124.1 \pm 17.7	92.4 \pm 8.1
6	126.9 \pm 2.9	124.0 \pm 7.7	97.9 \pm 8.0	112.8 \pm 14.0
10	152.6 \pm 19.2	111.4 \pm 9.0	120.5 \pm 12.0	85.1 \pm 12.5
11			92.9 \pm 13.0	
13			83.8 \pm 9.2	
15			95.5 \pm 11.7	
Control	100 \pm 14.1	100 \pm 16.5	100 \pm 14.1	100 \pm 16.5

Table S4. Percentages of viable CCRF-CEM cancer cells following treatment with nucleoside analogs.

Compound	Concentration		
	1 μM	10 μM	100 μM
1a	112.0 \pm 9.7	106.5 \pm 26.0	94.7 \pm 12.8
6	104.5 \pm 21.4	106.4 \pm 18.8	105.8 \pm 6.3
11	103.9 \pm 11.8	106.5 \pm 23.3	105.9 \pm 9.1
13	107.0 \pm 5.3	103.6 \pm 16.1	90.3 \pm 18.2
15	116.5 \pm 8.9	109.0 \pm 9.5	99.9 \pm 13.7

Table S5. Percentages of viable HL-60 cancer cells following treatment with nucleoside analogs.

Compound	Concentration		
	1 μM	10 μM	100 μM
1a	105.3 \pm 28.4	105.0 \pm 21.3	99.3 \pm 29.0
6	106.5 \pm 22.8	102.6 \pm 40.2	98.0 \pm 27.6
11	92.9 \pm 18.5	102.4 \pm 23.2	98.2 \pm 29.1
13	100.1 \pm 14.0	97.4 \pm 17.7	93.6 \pm 10.9
15	107.6 \pm 29.3	108.8 \pm 24.3	105.7 \pm 27.0

Figure S1. NOESY spectrum of compound **9**.

